

The Decision-Making Behaviour of Purchasing Products Through Online Media of Consumers in Chonburi Province

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Abstract:- This research aims to study demographic factors. Marketing factors and behavior in purchasing products via online media of consumers including the study of demographic factors and marketing factors that affect consumers' purchasing behavior via online media. The sample group used in the research study was 400 consumers in Mueang District, Chonburi Province, using an online questionnaire as a data collection tool. and use the obtained data to analyze the statistical results according to the research objectives with a ready-made program. The statistics used to analyze the data are descriptive statistics consisting of frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation. and quantitative statistics include Independent Sample t-test, Chi-square, and Multinomial Logistic Regression Analysis.

Major Findings: the majority of the sample were female, aged 21 - 25 years, with a certain level of education, bachelor's degree or equivalent, occupation: student, have a working period of less than 1 year and have an income of less than 15,000 baht. Most of the media used is Facebook. They have a purchasing behavior 1 - 2 times per month. and choose to buy at a price level of less than 1,000 baht. The results of the hypothesis testing found that demographic factors that affect the media used to purchase products are different, including age, educational level, occupation, work experience. and income level. Demographic factors that affect the frequency of purchasing products include gender. Demographic factors that affect the price level of purchasing products include gender, age, education level, occupation, work experience, and income. As for the study of marketing factors that affect the behavior of buying products through online media, it was found that the marketing factors that affect the media used by consumers to purchase products include product and price aspects. Marketing factors that affect the frequency of purchasing products by consumers include products. As for the price level of purchasing products, there is no market factor that affects it at all.

Keywords:- Buying Behavior; Online Media and Marketing Factors.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the past, the first behavior of buying and selling goods was that people would buy and sell goods by exchanging goods for goods. And later developed into exchanging goods with currency. Most of the time, consumers have a preference for purchasing products in stores or in shopping centers. convenience store Because they can touch and consider products or services according to their own preferences and needs. But nowadays, with technology and various communications, we have reached the point where there is an online information system that has developed greatly. In addition, the emergence of a new catastrophic disease, COVID-19, has caused people to avoid meeting each other and touching each other, which has led to an increase in buying and selling goods online. This is convenient for purchasing products in many steps, starting from the process of searching for product information of interest. Payment process that can be paid in many ways.

This rapid advancement in technology is the reason that today's trading system is different from before. which trade in the past It will be traded through the storefront only. As a result, there is a high use of money for investment in business operations. In addition, the traditional trade will provide access to such stores Accessible only to local customers. But in the era of change in the present situation Commercial businesses are increasingly using technology to help manage. which is popularly called e-commerce market, which such business operations It is the use of internet signals to communicate between sellers and customers. Because it is a worthwhile return without having to go through a middleman. (Ministry of Digital Economy and Society, 2017) This channel is therefore considered a virtual trading center where goods can be bought and exchanged freely. Can reach customers all over the world. with convenience and speed Information can be received from anywhere, anytime, 24 hours a day (Tanasak et al., 2017), making trading through such channels likely to increase continuously. Buying and selling products via electronic means is an important option for consumers who do not have time to purchase products at the store in person (Thitima Fan, 2015) because the electronic market is convenient for buying and selling and searching. (National Electronics and Computer Technology Center, 2010) As well as trends in consumer behavior in the future, they also place importance on time, ease, and convenience in purchasing products and services (Maneerat Rattanaphan, 2015).

Electronic Transactions Development Agency (ETDA) (ETDA), Ministry of Digital Economy and Society Revealing the results of the survey of the value of e-commerce in Thailand in 2021 or the Value of e-Commerce Survey in Thailand 2021, it was found that in 2020 the e-commerce business or e-commerce in Thailand had a value equal to 3.78 trillion baht, with a large proportion of the value of e-commerce in the B2C format. Ultimately, the value is more than 2.17 trillion baht, B2B is worth more than 0.84 trillion baht and B2G is worth 0.77 trillion baht. It is expected that the value of e-commerce in Thailand in 2021 will grow to 4.1 trillion baht. ETDA reveals the results of the e-commerce value survey. In Thailand, in 2020 it was equal to 3.78 trillion baht, which decreased from 2019 with a value of 4.05 trillion baht, or 6.68 percent, due to the COVID-19 epidemic situation. Resulting in measures to restrict international and domestic travel. Including the Work from Home measure, which has had a negative impact on the accommodation industry. transportation industry and the manufacturing industry is very Although the retail and wholesale industry continues to grow, Due to the change in behavior of Thai people who increasingly like to buy products and services online.

Fig.1 Value of Electronic Commerce in Thailand
Source: Electronic Transactions Development Agency, 2021

The value of e-commerce in 2021 is expected to have a continuous growth trend after recovery from the COVID-19 epidemic situation to 4.01 trillion baht or a growth of 6.11 percent from 2020, with the expected cumulative average growth rate. From 2017 to 2021, it is at 9.79 percent. Currently, there are a lot of online businesses and there is high competition. The above data shows that marketers should pay attention to changes in technology. and utilization of the internet for marketing operations As a result, the research team is interested in studying the attitudes of people purchasing online products and services in Chonburi Province. And because it is an interesting study Moreover, studying this relationship is new for online merchants in Chonburi province. And the results from this study can be used as guidelines for determining appropriate marketing strategies. To meet the needs of consumers to meet their needs as much as possible.

➤ *Research Objective*

- To study the behavior of purchasing products via online media of consumers in Chonburi Province.
- To study demographic factors that affects the behavior of consumers in choosing to buy products via online media in Chonburi Province
- To study marketing factors that affects the behavior of purchasing products via online media of consumers in Chonburi Province.

➤ *Research Hypothesis*

- Hypothesis 1: Consumers with different demographic factors there are different behaviors in deciding to buy products online.
- Hypothesis 2: Marketing factors influence consumers' decision to purchase products via online media in Chonburi Province.

➤ *Research Framework*

Fig 2 Research Framework

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Concepts and Theories About Demography

Demographic concepts Demographic characteristics, it is considered to be diverse and different about people, such as gender, age, status, and body structure. Seniority in work, etc. It will show the history of each person from the past to the present. This difference and diversity of individuals can indicate different behavioral characteristics. Different decisions are caused by differences in demographics or backgrounds of individuals (Wachirawat Ngamlamom, 2015). Demographic characteristics (Demographic) consisting of gender, age, status, education level, occupation, income are appropriate criteria. It is popularly used to group customers, consumers, and market segmentation. In addition, Hauser and Duncan The meaning of the word has been given. Demography: Demography is the study of the size, distribution, and composition of a population. (Composition) Study of changes and the components of such changes. Components of demographic change include birth, death, migration, and changes in social status. Nipon Thepwan (1980).

➤ *Demography has the Scope of Study in 4 Areas:*

- Study of the size of the population. The word size refers to the number of units in counting the population, such as the number - people. In this matter, it is a study to know what the population size is in any one area. Bigger or smaller than in the past? And what size will it be in the future?
- The study of population distribution. The word distribution refers to the grouping of the population in a certain area, whether in the form of geography or residential area at a given time. In this issue, we study how the population is distributed according to geography or residential areas, such as regions, provinces, rural areas, and cities. What are the causes of such distribution? And what changes have occurred as a result of this distribution of the population?
- Study of population composition In this issue, it is a study of various characteristics of the population clustered together in a particular area, such as gender, age, nationality, marital status, income, occupation, etc.
- Study of the components of demographic change The term demographic change refers to an increase or decrease in the total population. or of the population in some structure (Structure). All demographic changes include births, deaths, and migration. The structure is the distribution of the population according to gender and age. Therefore, this issue is a study of three important elements: birth, death, and migration. This will cause the population in any area to change.

Demographic variables used to divide market share include age, gender, status, family members. Education level, occupation, and monthly income is an important factor This can be measured quantitatively in the population and used to set business goals more efficiently and effectively than psychological data.

B. Concepts and Theories About Consumer Behavior

Consumer behavior is the conduct or behavior that a person provides. Using products or choosing to receive services The buyer or service recipient has needs. Have purchasing power by Kotler, 1999, cited by Siriwan Serirat et al., 2009. Summary of the definition of consumer behavior (Consumer behavior) is that it is the activities of consumers regarding the decision to acquire goods and services. This includes decision process and the actions of individuals related to purchasing and using products. Sukanya Payungsin (2013) gives the definition of consumer behavior. It means decision-making, purchasing, selecting and evaluating the use of products or services by individuals, which is important for purchasing goods and services. Supaporn Phumsilo (2013) defined consumption behavior as the expression of an individual that is directly related to the use of economic goods and services. Including the decision-making process that affects expression, that affects access to marketing Factors that influence consumer purchasing decisions Those involved can find ways to correct the behavior. in the consumer purchasing decision process Help develop the product development market, resulting in better quality. It is also useful in identifying market segments to respond to consumer needs. The important point is that the decision-making process pre-exists these antecedents. Refers to the behavioral characteristics of consumers that At any given moment the consumer purchases the product. He will have a psychological process. and various social societies that have always played a part in shaping and refining his attitude and

values since he was a child until he was an adult and at the point of purchase.

In studying the consumer market It is critical for marketers to understand the behaviors of consumers who are the most important component of the consumer market. In order to understand the cause or reason why Consumers decide to buy or not buy a particular product. Phillip Kotler explains the emergence of consumer behavior using S-R Theory as follows:

Motives that cause the decision to purchase the product It begins with the creation of a stimulus (Stimulus) that passes into the consumer's consciousness (Buyer's Black Box), which is like a black box that the manufacturer Or marketers cannot predict when consumers are aware of the stimulus and have a need, then a purchase or response (Response) will occur. The details are as follows.

- External stimuli of the buyer, what stimulates consumer desire can be caused by internal impulses such as hunger and thirst, or may be external stimuli such as marketing stimuli. and other stimulants, most marketers focus on external stimulants by trying to arrange external stimuli specifically, marketing stimuli can induce consumers to want to buy products. 1.1 Marketing Stimuli are those that marketers can control and provide. It is a stimulus related to the marketing mix, which consists of Product incentives such as designing products to be beautiful and eye-catching. Price incentives, such as setting payment terms or offering better discounts than competitors Stimulus for organizing distribution channels, such as having products widely available for sale. and marketing promotion incentives such as discounts, exchanges, giveaways Consistent advertising, these things if marketers can understand the needs of consumers. And being able to arrange marketing stimuli to suit the needs of customer groups will surely be a tool that can stimulate consumers to create demand. Which will eventually lead to buying behavior. 1.2. Other Stimuli Other Stimuli are those that are outside the organization and cannot be controlled by the marketer. These stimulants include: Economic stimulants such as the economic situation and income of consumers will affect the purchasing desire of consumers. technological stimulus such as modern and fast communication technology Makes consumers want to use mobile phones more Legal and political incentives. For example, a law increasing or decreasing taxes on a particular type of product will affect the demand for that type of product. And cultural stimuli such as customs and traditions in various festivals will stimulate demand for certain products during that festival, etc.
- Buyer's Black Box or buyer's feelings. It is the part that is influenced by the characteristics of the buyer, which is influenced by cultural factors Social factors Personal factors and psychological factors (which will be discussed in detail next) and is also influenced by the buyer decision process, that consists of 5 different steps: problem recognition Searching for information Evaluation of alternatives purchasing decision and post-purchase behavior (Details will be discussed in the Buyer Decision Process section.)

- Buyer's Responses. Buyer's Responses. or purchasing decisions of consumers Consumers will make decisions in various matters as follows: Selecting a product (Product Choice) that will meet their needs, such as choosing shrimp porridge for breakfast. Or choose fresh milk for breakfast. Choosing a brand, for example if you want to drink milk for breakfast. And what brand of fresh milk will you drink? Selecting a vendor (Dealer Choice), selecting a purchase time, selecting the purchase amount, etc. Consumer behavior analysis.

Consumer behavior analysis means analysis in order to understand All causes influence and cause consumers to decide to purchase products and services. By understanding the various causes that influence or direct consumer decisions, marketers will be able to successfully respond to consumers as well. being able to influence and convince customers to buy products and have the loyalty to buy again and again continuously Thongchai Santiwong (1982)

Therefore, analyzing consumer behavior Therefore, it is a matter of studying consumer decision-making and what influence factors determine it. or that is the cause of the decision to purchase as stated above. Behavior while making a purchase (What we have seen is the general action of customers) is therefore only the last step or the end of the cause. of the purchasing decision consideration process and in the purchasing decision of consumers or actual consumer behavior It consists of the influence of many different factors. Such as learning needs, preferences, attitudes, and understanding from social groups. As well as these cultural factors exist in the thoughts and hearts of everyone. Each of which has been created and refined according to the process according to their own thoughts and psychology. according to different social and cultural surroundings, from the past to the present. This causes the actual internal characteristics of consumers to vary as well.

C. Marketing Mix Concepts and Theories

McCarthy developed a marketing tool that has been accepted until now, namely the "Marketing Mix" or what is also known as "Marketing Mix". Marketing factors are important components of a 4-point marketing strategy, or 4Ps, consisting of product development, pricing, distribution channels, and promotion. To reach the target group, including stimulating the selection of products and services, which 4 principles will affect marketing communications. The target audience (McCarthy & Perreault, 1990) Kotler (1997) and Kotler and Keller (2012) explained that "Marketing Mix is an important concept in modern marketing. that can be controlled and used together to meet the satisfaction of the target group When the tool is used, it is considered to be the integration of all marketing decisions. The marketing mix can be divided into 7 groups as follows: product, price, distribution channel (Place), marketing promotion, people, physical characteristics and process. will be able to communicate effectively to the recipient"

From this theory, the researcher sees that Marketing factors influence the behavior of consumers in deciding to purchase products. Therefore, we use this concept to find answers about marketing factors, including products, prices, and distribution channels. and marketing promotions that affect consumers'

decision-making behavior in purchasing products through online media. Details are as follows:

A new concept about the marketing mix that has a more forward-looking view is the modern marketing mix (4Cs), which has the following ingredients:

- Responding to consumer needs (Consumer Needs and Wants) Determining the first marketing component regarding sales offerings. Therefore, it is necessary to create a wide scope in order to be consistent with the concept of marketing that emphasizes response.
- The cost of procuring something that will satisfy the demand (Cost to Buy) The price is a value set by the seller. and agreed to sell because the buyer accepted From the perspective of the buyer of the product, the price is the money that must be paid plus the seller's profit.
- The need for convenience to buy (Convenience to Buy) is a continuous relationship from considering the total cost of purchasing.
- Using communication tools in marketing promotion (Communication) due to advertising expenses has increased and there are many products through each type of advertising media. In the future, consumers will be increasingly under the influence of various communication tools. and is a communication tool that can directly reach consumers Businesses see that they should promote marketing through communication media that can reach more consumers and be cheaper.

D. Concepts and Theories Related to Purchasing Decisions

Consumer purchasing decision process It is the sequence of steps in the purchasing decision of the consumer. From a survey of many consumers in the purchasing process, it was found that The recipient will go through a 5-step process consisting of (1) searching for available information (2) searching for information (Information Search). Finding ways to make those needs satisfied. This may require effort and data analysis. (3) Evaluation of Alternatives is a step in the process. The purchasing decision in which the consumer evaluates the benefits that he or she will receive from each product choice. (4) Purchase Decision: The consumer determines satisfaction between fade various products that is optional Consumers decide to buy the product they like the most. (5) Post purchase behavior from consuming or using the product with expectations. The consumer may skip or return to the previous step. This shows that the buying process begins before the actual purchase. and has an impact after purchase (Armstrong and Kotler 2015). Recognition of problems (Problem Recognition) or recognition of needs occurs when people recognize the differences.

Related research Sitthisang and Panthong (2022) studied the matter. Factors influencing the decision to purchase products from the machine automatic vending machines of consumers in Bangkok. This research aims to Study the factors that influence consumers' decision to purchase products from automatic vending machines. Bangkok. Results of testing the hypothesis found that Personal factors, including gender, occupation, and income, affect the decision to purchase products from vending machines among consumers in Bangkok. In terms of marketing mix factors that influence purchasing decisions Products from vending machines of consumers in Bangkok, including product factors Distribution

channels, physical characteristics and process with a significance level of 0.05 and Nunthaegapong and Panthong (2022) studied the Factors that influence product purchasing decisions Supplement food for the health of working people from convenience stores in Bangkok. The objective of this research is to Study personal factors affecting the decision to purchase health supplements for working people from convenience stores. in Bangkok and marketing factors that influence consumers' decision to purchase health supplements. Working age people from convenience stores in Bangkok By the test of the hypothesis, it was found that Personal factors include educational level. and monthly income It affects the decision to purchase dietary supplements for the health of working people. Convenience stores in Bangkok As for the marketing factors that influence the decision to purchase dietary supplements for Health of working people from convenience stores in Bangkok, including products, marketing promotion, website, For online social media, and price, the statistical significance levels of 0.01 and 0.05 can together predict 47.70 percent.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The aim of this research is to study the factors affecting the decision-making behavior of purchasing products through online media of consumers in Mueang District, Chonburi Province. It is quantitative research. The study uses primary data. The researcher aims to study demographic factors. Marketing mix and the decision-making behavior of purchasing products through online media of consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province The survey used a questionnaire design. and tertiary data (Secondary Data) from related research various book articles and theories used to study the factors affecting the decision-making behavior of purchasing products through online media of consumers in Mueang District, Chonburi Province.

➤ Population

The target population used in this research study is consumers in Mueang District, Chonburi Province. Random sampling of consumers in Mueang District, Chonburi Province. Total number: 274,844 people.

➤ Sample Size

Consumer representative in Mueang District, Chonburi Province On average, questionnaires were distributed proportionally because the number of samples calculated was very different by using random sampling to be representative of the entire population. The sample size was set at a confidence level of 95 percent. By allowing a discrepancy of not more than 5 percent.

➤ Research Tools

The researcher used a questionnaire as a research tool. One questionnaire was divided into 4 parts as follows.

- This questionnaire was prepared with the aim of studying Factors affecting the decision-making behavior of purchasing products via online media

- This questionnaire is divided into 4 parts:
 - ✓ Part 1: Questions about demographic factors.
 - ✓ Part 2: Questions about behavior in choosing products via online media.
 - ✓ Part 3 Questions about The level of importance of purchasing products via online media based on the principles of the marketing mix.
 - ✓ Part 4: Additional suggestions regarding decision-making behavior in purchasing products through online media.

➤ *This Research was done by Finding Information from 2 Sources as Follows:*

• Primary Data

It is information obtained from answering questionnaires from sample groups in field data collection. The researcher must collect the questionnaires and check the questionnaires. to be used for statistical processing.

• Secondary Data

It is information that the researcher studies and researches information, concepts, and theories related to research from books, journals, articles, research, and various electronic media. In addition, the researcher has brought a completed questionnaire. Went to inquire with 400 consumers in Mueang District, Chonburi Province, by checking the accuracy of every questionnaire in detail. and analyze the results using a ready-made program.

➤ *The Statistics used in Data Analysis*

Statistics used in data analysis are descriptive statistics consisting of frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation. and quantitative statistics include Independent Sample t-test, Chi-square, and Multinomial Logistic Regression Analysis.

IV. RESULTS

➤ *Part 1 Results of the Analysis of Demographic Factors Include:*

The research results found that Most of the respondents were female, 284 people, accounting for 71.0 percent, and aged 21 - 25 years, 196 people, accounting for 49.0 percent, followed by those younger than 20 years, 85 people, accounting for 21.3 percent, and The fewest answers were 26 - 30 years old, 40 people, accounting for 10.0 percent. Most of the education was a bachelor's degree or equivalent. 267 people, accounting for 66.8 percent, mostly had occupations. Students/students, 208 people, accounting for 52.0 percent, followed by civil servants, 54 people, accounting for 13.5 percent. Most of their work experience has been less than 1 year, 202 people, accounting for 50.5 percent, followed by 6 years or more. There were 80 people, accounting for 20 percent, and the income level found that most had incomes less than 15,000 baht, 193 people, accounting for 48.3 percent, followed by 15,001 - 30,000 baht, 153 people, accounting for 38.0 percent.

➤ Summary of Hypothesis Test Results

Table 1 Hypothesis H₁

Hypothesis H ₁	Test Results	
	accept	reject
1. Demographic factors affecting online purchasing behavior		
1.1. Different genders affect the media used to purchase products by consumers. In Mueang District, Nakhru Pathom Province is different		✓
1.2. Different genders affect the frequency of purchasing products by consumers. In Mueang District, Chonburi Province, it is different	✓	
1.3. Different genders affect the price level of purchasing products. Consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province is different	✓	
1.4. Different ages affect the media used by consumers to purchase products. In Mueang District, Chonburi Province, it is different	✓	
1.5. Different ages affect the frequency of consumer purchases. In Mueang District, Chonburi Province, it is different		✓
1.6. Different ages affect the price level of purchasing products. Consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province is different	✓	
1.7. Different levels of education affect the media used to purchase products. of consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province is different	✓	
1.8. Different educational levels affect the frequency of purchasing products. of consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province is different		✓
1.9. Different levels of education affect the purchase price. Products of consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province is different	✓	
1.10. Different professions affect the media used to purchase products. Consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province is different	✓	
1.11. Different occupations affect the frequency of purchasing products. Consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province is different		✓
1.12. Different occupations affect the price level of purchasing products. Consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province is different.	✓	
1.13. Different work experiences affect the media used for purchasing. Products of consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province is different.	✓	
1.14. Different work experiences affect the frequency of purchases. Products of consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province is different.		✓
1.15. Different work experiences affect the price level of purchasing products. of consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province is different.	✓	
1.16. Different income levels affect the media used to purchase products. of consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province is different.	✓	
1.17. Different income levels affect the frequency of purchasing products. of consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province is different.		✓
1.18. Different income levels affect the purchase price level. Products of consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province is different.	✓	

Table 2 Hypothesis H₂

Hypothesis H ₂	Test Results	
	accept	reject
2. Marketing factors that affect purchasing behavior via online media		
2.1.1 Product marketing factors affect the media used. Buy consumer products in Mueang District Chonburi Province.	✓	
2.1.2 Marketing factors that affect the price of the media used for purchasing Products of consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province.	✓	
2.1.3 Marketing factors in terms of distribution channels affect the media. used to purchase consumer products in Mueang District Chonburi Province.		✓
2.1.4 Marketing factors in terms of marketing promotion affect the media used in Consumer purchases in Mueang District Chonburi Province.		✓
2.2.1 Product marketing factors affect the frequency of Buy consumer products in Mueang District Chonburi Province.	✓	
2.2.2 Price marketing factors affect purchasing frequency. Products of consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province.		✓
2.2.3 Marketing factors in terms of distribution channels affect Frequency of purchasing products by		✓

Hypothesis H ₂	Test Results	
	accept	reject
2. Marketing factors that affect purchasing behavior via online media consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province.		
2.2.4 Marketing factors in marketing promotions affect frequency. In purchasing products from consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province.		✓
2.3.1 Product marketing factors affect the price level in Consumer purchases in Mueang District Chonburi Province.		✓
2.3.2 Price marketing factors affect the purchase price level. Products of consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province.		✓
2.3.3 Marketing factors regarding distribution channels affect. Price level for purchasing products by consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province.		✓
2.3.4 Marketing factors in terms of marketing promotion affect the level. Prices for purchasing goods by consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province.		✓

V. DISCUSSION

➤ *Hypothesis 1: Different Demographic Factors there are Different Behaviors in Deciding to Buy Products Online.*

The results of the hypothesis testing found that: Different genders have no different effect on the decision-making behavior of purchasing products via online media, indicating that whether consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province Whether they are female or male, they all have the same behavior in deciding to buy products via online media. Because the business of selling products through online media today has continued to grow as a result of greatly advanced technology. Make it easier and faster for consumers to access. Consistent with the research of Piyamaporn Chuaychuhon (2016), he conducted a research study on factors influencing the decision to purchase products through online social media. It was found that different gender demographic factors affect purchasing decisions. Products through online social media are no different. And the research of Jutharat Kiattirasamee (2015) conducted a research study on factors affecting the purchase of products through online applications by consumers in Bangkok and surrounding areas. Studying differences in demographic factors. Research results It was found that different gender factors affected the decision to purchase products via online applications among sample groups in Bangkok and surrounding areas.

Different genders affect the frequency of purchasing products per month for consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province found that different genders have different effects on the frequency of purchasing products per month, indicating that whether consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province Whether female or male, the frequency of purchasing products per month is different. Consistent with the research of Apaporn Wattanakul (2012), factors related to consumer purchasing behavior through electronic commerce websites. It was found that consumers of different genders have different behavior in buying products through popular e-commerce websites in Thailand. They differ in terms of the frequency of purchasing products through e-commerce websites. Popular games of Thailand

Different genders affect the price level of each purchase by consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province found that different genders have different effects on the price level purchased each time, showing that whether consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province Whether it's female or male, there will be a price level. The names are different each time. Parama

Setavetin said: Males and females differ greatly in their ideas, preferences, and attitudes. This is because culture and society define different roles and activities for the two sexes.

Different ages affect the media used to purchase products by consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province found that different ages have different effects on the media used to purchase products, indicating that whether consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province No matter what age they are, they have different behavior in deciding to buy products via online media. Consistent with the research of Mayuree Tangphanthong (2009), the study of factors related to the behavior of purchasing goods and services via the Internet among consumers in Bangkok found that different age factors influence the behavior of purchasing goods and services through the internet. different internet

Different ages affect the frequency of purchases per month of consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province found that different ages have no different effect on the frequency of purchasing products per month, indicating that whether consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province What age will they be in? The frequency of purchasing products per month is also no different. Consistent with the research of Apaporn Wattanakul (2012), factors related to consumer purchasing behavior through popular electronic commerce websites in Thailand. The research results found that Demographic characteristics of age Different types of consumers affect consumer purchasing behavior through popular e-commerce websites in Thailand. In terms of purchasing frequency, there is no difference at the statistical significance level of 0.05.

Different ages affect the price level of each purchase of consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province Different ages have different effects on the price level purchased each time, indicating that consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province with different age groups will buy products in The price level of each purchase is different. This is consistent with the research of Pichamon Malikhao (2011) on the study of factors affecting the behavior of purchasing women's fashion clothing through the online market on Facebook, it was found that customers of different ages had different decisions to purchase women's clothing through the online market on Facebook, especially in terms of value. Spend on each order

Different levels of education affect the media used by consumers to purchase products. It was found that different levels of education have different effects on the media used to purchase products, indicating that consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province People with different levels of education will have different behavior in deciding to buy products via online media. This is consistent with the research of Pichamon Malikhao (2011) on the study of factors affecting women's fashion clothing buying behavior. Through social media Facebook The research results found that Customers with different educations have different purchasing habits for women's fashion clothing. Through different social media Facebook

Different levels of education affect the frequency of purchases per month of consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province found that different levels of education had no different effect on the frequency of purchasing products per month, indicating that whether consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province There will be an education level in any range. The frequency of purchasing products per month is not different. Consistent with the research of Apaporn Wattanakul (2012), factors related to consumer purchasing behavior through popular electronic commerce websites in Thailand. The results of the research found that the demographic characteristics of Highest level of education Different types of consumers affect consumer purchasing behavior through popular e-commerce websites in Thailand. In terms of purchasing frequency, there is no difference at the statistical significance level of 0.05.

Different educational levels have an effect on the price level purchased each time by consumers in Mueang District, Chonburi Province. It was found that different educational levels have different effects on the price level purchased each time, indicating that Consumption in Mueang District Chonburi Province People with different levels of education will buy products at different prices each time. This is in line with the research of Chaiwat Phitakraktham (2013) who studied the subject. Factors related to consumers' decision to purchase products online The research results found that The demographic factors of different educational levels affect the maximum amount of money ever purchased by different consumers at the significance level of 0.05.

Different occupations affect the media used to purchase products by consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province found that different occupations have different effects on the media used to purchase products, indicating that consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province People with different occupations will have different behavior in deciding to buy products via online media. Consistent with the research of Jutharat Kiattirasamee (2015), he conducted a research study on factors affecting the purchase of products through online applications by consumers in Bangkok and surrounding areas. Studying the differences in demographic factors, the research found that Different career factors It affects the decision to purchase products via online applications among sample groups in Bangkok and surrounding areas differently, with the group of students having a higher average purchase decision than those with careers as employees of private companies. This may be a result of duties and responsibilities. Resulting in having to think before making a purchase. Because the group of students does not have any income yet. and did not earn money by himself When you get

money from your parents, you can make purchasing decisions more easily.

Different occupations affect the frequency of purchasing products per month for consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province found that different occupations had no different effect on the frequency of purchasing products per month, indicating that consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province People with different occupations have the same frequency of purchasing products per month. Consistent with the research of Apaporn Wattanakul (2012), factors related to consumer purchasing behavior through popular electronic commerce websites in Thailand. The research results found that Occupational demographic characteristics Different types of consumers affect consumer purchasing behavior through popular e-commerce websites in Thailand. In terms of purchasing frequency, there is no difference at the statistical significance level of 0.05.

Different occupations affect the price level of each purchase of consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province found that different occupations have different effects on the price level purchased each time, indicating that consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province People with different occupations will buy products at different price levels each time they purchase them. This is in line with the research of Chaiwat Phitakraktham (2013) who studied the subject. Factors related to consumers' decision to purchase products online The research results found that Different occupational demographic factors influence the maximum amount of money ever purchased by different consumers at the 0.05 significance level.

Different work experiences have different effects on the media used to purchase products by consumers. It was found that different work experiences have different effects on the media used to purchase products, indicating that consumers In Mueang District Chonburi Province People with different work experiences have different behavior in deciding to buy products via online media. Because the theory of individual differences (DeFleur, 1996) has proposed the basic principles of the theory of individual differences that Learning about the environment creates attitudes, values, and beliefs that embody character. Personal psychology that is different This difference has become a condition. that determines news perception plays an important role in news perception

Different experiences affect the frequency of purchasing products per month of consumers in Mueang district. Chonburi Province found that different work experiences had no effect on the frequency of purchasing products per month, indicating that consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province People with different work experiences have the same frequency of purchasing products per month. This is because consumers with more or less work experience The same stimulus must be used to purchase. The consumer behavior model regarding external stimuli stipulates that If marketers can understand the needs of consumers And being able to arrange marketing stimuli to suit the needs of customer groups will surely be a tool that can stimulate consumers to create demand. This will eventually lead to buying behavior.

Different work experiences affect the price level purchased each time by consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province found that different work experiences affect the price level purchased each time by consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province shows that consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province People with different work experiences have different levels of purchase price each time. Prama Setawetin (1990) has stated that Different work experiences give people different needs. In terms of shared values and the price level of that product

Different income levels affect the media used by consumers to purchase products. of consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province found that different income levels have different effects on the media used to purchase products, indicating that consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province People with different income levels have different behavior in deciding to buy products via online media. Consistent with the research of Ekthat Panich Raksaphong (2016) studied the Factors affecting the decision to purchase books through the online book distribution channel of Nai In Bookstore. The research results found that Different average monthly income affects the degree to which they decide to purchase books through the website. www.naiin.com is different.

Different income levels affect the frequency of monthly purchases of consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province found that different income levels had no effect on the frequency of purchasing products per month, indicating that consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province People with different income levels will have the same frequency of purchasing products per month. This is in line with the research of Chaiwat Phitakraktham (2013) who studied the subject. Factors that are related to consumers' decision to purchase products online. The research found that Different income demographic factors did not affect the number of purchases made in different 12-month periods at the 0.05 significance level.

Different income levels affect the price level of each purchase of consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province found that different income levels have different effects on the price level purchased each time, indicating that consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province People with different income levels will buy products at different prices each time. Consistent with the research of Pichamanchu Malikhao (2011) on the study of factors affecting women's fashion clothing purchasing behavior. Through social media Facebook The research results found that Customers with different incomes have different buying habits for women's fashion clothes. Through different social media Facebook Especially in terms of expenses spent each time. This is in line with the research of Chaiwat Phitakraktham (2013) who studied the subject. Factors related to consumers' decision to purchase products online The sample group used in the research was 384 consumers who used internet services who had ordered products and services online. A questionnaire was used as a tool to collect data. The research results found that Different income demographic factors affect the maximum amount a consumer purchases at any one time. Because income is a reflection of purchasing ability, which is considered an important factor in deciding to purchase products at a price level that they can spend. This results in differences in purchasing goods between those with high incomes and those with low incomes.

➤ *Hypothesis 2: Marketing Factors Influence Consumers' Decision to Purchase Products via Online Media in Chonburi Province.*

• *Hypothesis 2.1: Marketing Factors Influence the Media used to Purchase Products by Consumers in Mueang District, Chonburi Province.*

Marketing factors affect the media used to purchase products by consumers in Mueang District, Chonburi Province.

Product marketing factors affect the media used to purchase products by consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province found that product marketing factors affect the media used to purchase products by consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province Due to factors that affect consumers' purchasing decisions. is an external factor which is information about the product (Sirin Suengsunthon, 1999) The product therefore affects the media used by consumers to purchase the product.

Price marketing factors affect the media used to purchase products by consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province found that the marketing factor of price has an effect on the media used to purchase products by consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province Because price is an important factor that will attract consumers. The consumer will compare it with other media. In order to get the right price according to customer needs.

Marketing factors regarding distribution channels affect the media used to purchase products by consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province found that marketing factors in terms of distribution channels had no effect on the media used to purchase products by consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province Because the distribution channels from all media are no different and can be easily accessed. and convenient in selecting products for consumers Marketing factors regarding distribution channels therefore do not affect the media used to purchase consumer products.

Marketing factors in terms of marketing promotion affect the media used to purchase products by consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province found that marketing factors in terms of marketing promotion had no effect on the media used to purchase products by consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province Because of the marketing promotion aspects of all forms of media, similar activities are organized. Therefore, marketing promotion factors do not affect the media used to purchase products by consumers.

• *Hypothesis 2.2.: Marketing Factors Influence the Frequency of Purchasing Products by Consumers in Mueang District, Chonburi Province*

Product marketing factors affect the frequency of purchasing products by consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province found that product marketing factors affect the frequency of purchasing products by consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province This is in line with the research of Chaiwat Phitakraktham (2013) who studied the subject. Factors related to consumers' decision to purchase products online The research results found that Product marketing factors are related to the number of times products are ordered in the past 12 months.

Price marketing factors affect the frequency of purchasing products by consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province found that the marketing factor of price has no effect on the frequency of purchasing products by consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province Because online media has similar prices for each type of product. The frequency of purchase does not depend on the price of the product. But it depends on the needs or needs of that product. Therefore, price marketing factors do not affect the frequency of purchasing products by consumers.

Marketing factors regarding distribution channels affect the frequency of purchasing products by consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province found that marketing factors in terms of distribution channels have no effect on the frequency of purchasing products by consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province This is in line with the research of Chaiwat Phitakraktham (2013) who studied the subject. Factors that are related to consumers' decision to purchase products online. The research found that Factors in distribution channels have no relationship with the number of times products are ordered in the past 12 months.

Marketing factors in terms of marketing promotion affect the frequency of purchasing products by consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province found that marketing factors in terms of marketing promotion had no effect on the frequency of purchasing products by consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province Nowadays, all media that are traded online have similar marketing activities. Therefore, marketing promotion factors do not affect the frequency of purchasing products by consumers.

• *Hypothesis 2.3: Marketing Factors Influence the Price Level of Purchasing Products by Consumers in Mueang District, Chonburi Province*

Product Marketing factors influence the price level of purchasing products by consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province found that product marketing factors had no effect on the price level of purchasing products by consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province At present, the format of products will change according to social factors. Products on online media are similar in terms of quality and appearance. Therefore, product marketing factors do not affect the price level of purchasing products by consumers.

Marketing factors affecting price Price level for purchasing consumer products in Mueang District Chonburi Province found that the market factor in price has no effect on the price level of purchasing products by consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province This is because the price is a value set by the seller. and agreed to sell because the buyer accepted From the perspective of the product buyer The price factor therefore does not affect the price level of purchasing products by consumers.

Marketing factors regarding distribution channels affect Price level for purchasing products by consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province found that marketing factors in distribution channels have no effect on the price level of purchasing products by consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province This is because the distribution channels from all media have different product price levels. easily accessible And it is convenient for consumers to choose products. Marketing factors

in terms of distribution channels therefore do not affect the price level of consumers' purchases of products.

Marketing factors in terms of marketing promotion affect the price level of purchasing products by consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province found that marketing factors in terms of marketing promotion had no effect on the price level of purchasing products by consumers in Mueang District. Chonburi Province Nowadays, all media that are traded online have similar marketing activities. Marketing factors in terms of marketing promotion therefore have no effect on Price level of consumer purchases.

VI. SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

➤ *Suggestions*

From the study of Factors affecting the purchasing decision behavior of consumers in Mueang District Chonburi Province The researcher is of the opinion that Entrepreneurs who do business through social media can use the study results as follows.

- From the results of the study of demographic factors People who do online business Such information can be used to plan marketing strategies, for example, the channel that consumers use to purchase products most frequently is Facebook. Those who conduct business through online media This information can be used in promotions. and organize activities through Facebook to get the most response from consumers
- From the study of product marketing mix factors that affects consumers' decision-making behavior to purchase products through online media In terms of media used for purchases and frequency of purchases, this means stores that have a variety of products of good quality that meet the needs of consumers. and is different from general stores To create something new and interesting for customers and decide to buy products
- From the study of the factors of the marketing mix regarding price that affects consumers' decision-making behavior to purchase products through online media In terms of media used to purchase products Therefore, the price should be set that is appropriate. To meet the needs of customers and finally decide to buy the product

➤ *Suggestions for Next Research*

- In the next research, the population and sample should be increased to include consumers who have never purchased products or services through online media. Using a variety of individual or group interview methods. To get information in many ways to improve and develop business in the online market
- In the next research, other factors that affect the decision to buy products in the online market should be added. To be able to improve the marketing strategy according to customer needs.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Jutharat Kiattirasamee. (2015). Factors affecting purchasing products through online applications by consumers in Bangkok and surrounding areas. (Independent Study, Business Administration Degree), Master's Degree Thammasat University.
- [2]. Chaiwat Phitakraktham. (2013). Factors related to consumers' decision to purchase online products. (Master of Business Thesis), Rajamangala University of Technology Phra Nakhon.
- [3]. Chaowalit Haemathulin. (2014). Determining content validity of IOC. Retrieved from <http://chaowalit2555.blogspot.com>
- [4]. Piyamaporn Chuaychunu. (2016). Factors influencing the decision to purchase products through online social media. (Master of Business Administration Degree), Thammasat University.
- [5]. Pichamonchu Malikhao. (2011). Factors affecting women's fashion clothing buying behavior. Through social media Facebook. (Master's Degree, Rajamangala University of Technology Thanyaburi.
- [6]. Phisit Pojanjaruwit. (2015). Marketing factors affecting the selection of products and services at traditional retail stores in the Dusit area. *Panyapiwat Journal*, Year 7 (Special Issue), 39-51.
- [7]. PricewaterhouseCoopers Thailand. (2016). Survey results of global retail business trends for the year 2016. Retrieved from <http://www.manager.com.th/iBizChannel>
- [8]. Mayuree Tangphanthong. (2009). Factors related to the behavior of purchasing products and services via the internet of consumers in Bangkok. Graduate School, Thonburi University, Bangkok.
- [9]. Sira Inthakamthonchai. (2016). Survey results of global retail business trends for the year 2016. Retrieved from <http://www.manager.co.th/iBizChanneViewNews.aspx?NewsID=9590000039294>
- [10]. National Statistical Office. (2014). Survey of the status of electronic commerce in Thailand in 2013. Retrieved from https://www.msociety.go.th/article_attach/13436
- [11]. Suratchada Cherdboonmuang, Jirawut Lalprakon, & Wisut Klahan. (2014). Marketing factors and purchasing behavior through electronic commerce systems of consumers in Bangkok. *Panyapiwat Journal*, Year 5 (Special Issue), 76-91.
- [12]. Apaporn Wattanakul. (2012). Factors related to consumer purchasing behavior through popular electronic commerce websites in Thailand. (Master of Business Administration), Graduate School of Srinakharinwirot University.
- [13]. Amphon Nawawongsathian. (2014). Consumer decision-making behavior in online stores in Bangkok. *Panyapiwat Journal*, Year 5 (Issue 2), 134-149.
- [14]. Wachirawat Ngamlamom. (2015). Concepts and theories related to demographic characteristics 2016. Searched 5 years ago May 2023, from http://learningofpublic.blogspot.com/2015/09/blogpost_11.html.
- [15]. Siriwan Serirat et al. (2009). Modern marketing management. Bangkok: Thammasan Company Limited.
- [16]. Sukanya Payungsin. (2013). Consumer behavior. (Electronic textbook). Retrieved June 25, 2023 from http://202.28.120.18/2009/online/main_MK2/main.html.
- [17]. Suthip Pratum and Saranee Usenyang. (2022). Acceptance of information technology in the new way of life era. *Lawasri Journal of Thepsatri Rajabhat University*, 6(1), 1-18.
- [18]. Feng, C. P., & Chuan, C. S. (2013). Enhancing Competitive Advantage Of Hospitals Through Linguistics Evaluation On Customer Perceived Value. *Journal of American Academy of Business*, 5, 481-485.
- [19]. Kotler & Keller. (2012). *Marketing Management (14th ed.)*. Pearson Education Limited.
- [20]. Mathieson, K., Peacock, E., & Chin, W. W. (2001). Extending the technology acceptance model: the influence of perceived user resources. *ACM SIGMIS Database: the DATABASE for Advances in Information Systems*, 32(3), 86-112.
- [21]. Yamane, T. (1973). *Statistic: An introductory analysis*. (3rd ed.). New York: Harper and Row.
- [22]. Nunthaegapong, W. and Panthong, S. (2022). Factors Affecting Decisions of Working-Age Population to Purchase Dietary Supplements from Convenience Stores in Bangkok. *Journal of Innovation and Management*, Suan Sunandha Raiabhat University, 7(1), 96-109. (in Thai)
- [23]. Sitthisang, A. and Panthong, S. (2022). Factors Influencing Consumers' Decision to Buy Products from Vending Machines in Bangkok. *Suthiparitat Journal*. 36(1), 42-60. (in Thai)